

02.05.2022

SUB: INTERNSHIP COMPLETION LETTER

To Whomsoever it may concern

This is to certify that Aditya Girish Keshwain
(College: Srinivas University, Pandeshwar campus;
College ID:2SU19ID001; Branch: Interior design)
has successfully completed 102 days internship program at
Nayak Pai and Associates.

During the internship, he was exposed to the various activities in
interior design.

We found him extremely inquisitive and hard working. He was
very much interested to learn the function of our division and
also willing to put his best efforts and get in to the depth of the
subject to understand it better.

His association with us was very fruitful and we wish him all the
best in his future endeavors.

Warm Regards,

Suresh Pai
2/5/22

Suresh Pai P

Suresh Pai P., B.E., M.I.E., FIV
CONSULTING ENGINEER & VALUER
Nayak Pai & Associates
Krishna Prasad Building, Lalbagh
MANGALURU - 575003

HONEYCOMB L S D. World Of Interior, Mangalore, KARNATAKA, INDIA

+91 910 85 85 009
+91 910 85 85 855

DESIGN@HONEYCOMBLIFE.IN

INTERNSHIP COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

DATE: 05/04/2022

This is to certify that Miss. Divya H R [2SU20ID701] of 6th semester Bsc Interior Design, Srinivas University, Mangalore has completed her internship at our firm 4/1/2022 to 4/5/2022.

For Honeycomb LSD

Lohith Bangera

interior Designer /
Architect

LEGAL-TECH

ARCHITECTS & ENGINEERS, ADVOCATES & LEGAL CONSULTANTS
RERA, RE-DEVELOPMENT, REAL ESTATE AND PROJECT MANAGEMENT CONSULTANTS

VIJAY K BAGARIA

B.ARCH, AIIA, DIDD, LL.B
DIRECTOR AND PRINCIPAL CONSULTANT

OFFICE : B-01, MAHAVIR SMRUTI CHSL, 113/114, GARODIA
NAGAR, GHATKOPAR (EAST), MUMBAI 400077, INDIA.
MOBILE : +91 93222 89495 E-mail : legaltech02@gmail.com

- PROJECT MANAGEMENT CONSULTANTS (PMC) FOR RE-DEVELOPMENT OF HOUSING SOCIETIES, MHADA, CESED AND PRIVATE E
- ARCHITECTURE, CONSTRUCTION MANAGEMENT AND IN
- DEEMED CONVEYANCE, TITLE SEARCH, STAMP DUTY DRAFTING AND VETTING OF LEGAL DOCUMENTS.
- GOVT. APPROVALS AND LIASONING IN MCGM, MHADA, (AND OTHER AUTHORITIES.
- RERA, MOFA, CO-OP SOCIETY LAW, RENT ACT, REAL CONSUMER COURT, SUCCESSION, LITIGATION AND LEGAL

Date :- 23rd April, 2022

To,

Ms. Manali .A. Shirsekar,
Srinivas University, Mangalore-575001
Karnataka

Sub:- certificate of completion of internship.

This is to certify that Ms. Manali .A. Shirsekar, student of BSC. Interior design has completed 3 months internship with us , from 21st Jan, 2022 to 22th April.

As part of her internship she has done study on material knowledge, analysis of commercial space (office) and residential space.

During the tenure with us, we found Ms. Manali. A. Shirsekar, sincere and result oriented.

We wish Ms. Manali A. Shirsekar all the best for her future endeavors.

VIJAY B

VIJAY K. BAGARIA (DIRECTOR)
B. ARCH ,DIDD,LLB, CONTACT NO :- +919322289495

VIJAY BAGARIA

ARCHITECT
INTERIOR DESIGNER
CA/ 2001/ 28120
RAVINDRAY PRESS, TILAK RD.
GHATKOPAR (E), MUMBAI -400 077
CL (OFF) 516 7722 (RES) 516 9186

April 10th 2022

TO WHOME IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Vishakh s a student Srinivas university, Mangalore has successfully completed his industrial Training In our organization from 20th December 2021- 10th April 2022.

For Agac interiors Thiruvalla kerala

H O U Z Z
INTERIOR ARCHITECTURE & DESIGN

TO WHOME IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **SHAHEEN.ID No.2SU19ID013**, a student of Interior Designing Srinivas university College of Management and Science worked under my supervision during her internship period and she worked at **Houzz Interior Architecture and Design, Kasaragod**. I am pleased to state that she worked hard preparing this report and she has been able to present a good picture of concerned works. This information and findings presented in report seems to be authentic.

SHAHEEN Possesses a good moral character and pleasing personality. I wish her every success in future career.

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AHAMMED KABEER.M

Interior Architect.

Houzz.

interior architecture and design.

Kasaragod.

Ahmed Kabeer M

Dated: 30Th March 2022

To,
The Dean,
Srinivas University,
College Of Management & Commerce,
Department Of Interior Design,
City Campus, Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575 001.

Sub: Certificate Of Completion Of Internship

This Is To Certify That Mr. Manoj Keshav Salyan – 2SU19ID009, A Student Of Your College, Has Successfully Completed His Internship At DS Interiors From 19Th January 2022 To 30Th March 2022.

During His Internship, He Was Exposed To Various Aspects Of Designing & Supervising. We Found Him Sincere, Hardworking And Punctual. We Take This Opportunity To Thank Mr. Manoj Keshav Salyan And Wish Him All The Very Best For His Future.

Yours Sincerely,

For 'DS Interiors'

H O U Z Z
INTERIOR ARCHITECTURE & DESIGN

TO WHOME IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that AHAMMED ANAS.ID No.2SU19ID002, a student of Interior Designing Srinivas university College of Management and Science worked under my supervision during his internship period and he worked at Houzz Interior Architecture and Design,Kasaragod.I am pleased to state that he worked hard preparing this report and he has been able to present a good picture of concerned works. This information and findings presented in report seems to be authentic.

AHAMMED ANAS Possesses a good moral character and pleasing personality.I wish him every success in future career.

AHAMMED KABEER.M

Interior Architect,

Houzz,

interior architecture and design.

Kasaragod

Ahmed Kabeer M

RIDHIMA SHETTY
ARCHITECTURE & DESIGN

☎ 973 993 0232 // 934 334 3115

✉ ridhimashettydesigns@gmail.com

📍 7th floor,
Paramount West Gate,
Balmatta, Mangalore

PROFESSIONAL TRAINING CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Arshiya Mohammed Khan from Srinivas University, College of Management & Commerce, Department of Interior Design, Pandeshwar has interned at Ridhima Shetty Architecture and Design from 11/01/2022 to 23/04/2022. With a total of 90 working days.

Name: *Ridhima Shetty*

Designation: *CEO*

RIDHIMA SHETTY DESIGN STUDIO
COA Reg. No: CA/2017/8359
7th Floor, Paramount Westgate
Balmatta, MANGALURU - 575 003